

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plans and Activities v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-IA	5G Infrastructure Association
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GA	Grant Agreement
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union - Telecommunication Sector
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MWC	Mobile World Congress
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
PO	Project Officer
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RTOs	Research and Technology Organisations
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

D6.1 is associated to the Task 6.1 – “Dissemination and Communication Activities” (led by CTTC), which implements the dissemination and communication of the project goals, reports, results, achievements, and other outputs.

In particular, this initial deliverable on dissemination and communication activities identifies the target audiences, ranging from general public through scientific and academic communities up to specific 5G stakeholders and market actors. In addition, the dissemination and communication channels and actions are defined, while a thorough communication plan is developed, which incorporates innovative methods for sharing information with the public and interested stakeholders, in accordance with the dissemination strategy.

This deliverable will set the basis for the upcoming D6.2 and D6.3 (interim and final report, respectively), which will detail the dissemination and communication activities until the end of the project.

2 Introduction

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of CAM under realistic conditions. In particular, it will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland. This will help to boost confidence and accelerate the deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services throughout Europe. It also aims at validating 5G as a true enabler of innovative CAM services that cannot be realised by today's technology. Specifically, 5G-ROUTES will provide as specified in [1] :

- a) Validation of >150 network, business and service-level KPIs for 13 diverse CAM use cases that require 5G performance capabilities, covering several V2X scenarios in automated cooperative, awareness and sensing driving. 5G-ROUTES also focuses on uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go and multimodal services in the context of complete connectivity-enabled ecosystems around passengers and cargo over 3 different modes of transport (vehicles, rails and maritime)
- b) Innovative AI-based technological enablers for facilitating the execution of the field trials. Several scenarios will be considered for each use case covering cross-border, cross-telecom operators, cross telco-vendors, integrated cross terrestrial-satellite and cross-transport-mode settings. These will be incrementally validated, starting from lab trials, followed by localized large-scale trials at strategic cross-border locations (Valga city, Tallinn & Gulf of Finland) and finally in larger-scale trials covering significant portions of transport routes along the selected corridor.

The technical contributions of 5G-ROUTES are, without doubt, the main priority of the project. However, the dissemination of the developed ideas and the obtained results to a wide audience, ranging from the research community to non-scientific public, is critical for the overall success and the impact of the project on the society. WP6 aims at increasing the visibility of 5G-ROUTES by coordinating the activities related to the dissemination of the results and the communication of the proposed solutions. To that end, a set of tools has been created to promote the 5G-ROUTES solutions both to the expert and non-expert audience. This deliverable of WP6 presents the initial dissemination and communication plan of 5G-ROUTES.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed (see Table 1).

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES Task		Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
Task 6.1 - Dissemination and communication activities	<i>Implement the dissemination of the project goals, software products, reports, results, achievements, and other outputs. The target audiences will be identified, ranging from general public through scientific and academic communities up to specific 5G stakeholders and market actors. The dissemination and communication channels and actions will serve as a baseline to achieve the goals in this task.</i>	Sec.3 Sec.4	<i>The target audience for the dissemination and communication activities have been identified, along with the respective channels.</i>
	Dissemination of publications and white papers: <i>Along the project, the 5G-ROUTES partners will be involved in the preparation and publication of articles in scientific journals, peer-reviewed conferences, and books. The approved publications will be available in the internal document repository of the consortium, and those with appropriate copyright permissions will be publicly available through the project's website.</i>	Sec 3	D6.1 identifies the KPI for this D&C activity. D6.2 and D6.3 will include the publications and white papers in the context of 5G-ROUTES
	Joint dissemination actions and events: <i>The project's intermediate results will also be presented in form of white papers, presentations and online demos in various conferences and industrial exhibitions with the purpose of commercially exploiting 5G-ROUTES results and identifying new partners for collaboration in the EU market. To further amplify the potential of the initiative, the following options will be considered: (i) joint organisation with other relevant 5G-PPP projects, (ii) co-hosting in the framework of other well-established events, (iii) organisation of a session with other 5G stakeholders, (iv) cooperation with 5G-PPP WGs and mapping of results.</i>	Sec. 3	D6.1 identifies the KPI for this D&C activity. D6.2 and D6.3 will include future dissemination actions.

	<p>Communication media: Ensure the creation and constant update of all web-based communication means, including the project's website (from M01 by EBOS). Participants will also ensure visibility of the project activities through a number of traditional and electronic dissemination material edited electronically and sent out to a large pool of stakeholders on a quarterly basis. Implement the communication plan of the project and its associated activities. Relevant activities include: (i) create and publish visual representations of information, data or knowledge intended to present complex information quickly and clearly; (ii) provide effective support to dissemination and exploitation activities, whilst ensuring effective and appropriate communication towards various stakeholders, (iii) foster community building and realise impact on industry and research in Europe and worldwide, (iv) gather feedback from relevant stakeholders through networking activities, and (v) monitor/evaluate communication and dissemination activities.</p>	Sec. 4	The website has been already set up. Future activities will be reported in D6.2 and D6.3.
	<p>Development of the communication plan: Development of the communication plan, which will incorporate innovative methods for sharing information with the public and interested stakeholders.</p>	Sec. 5 Sec. 6 Sec. 7	The dissemination and communication phases have been defined. The detailed activities will be provided in D6.2 and D6.3.
	<p>Tutorials & PhD schools: Organisation of 3 tutorials under the framework of important IEEE conferences and 2 PhD schools to inspire students to become the future generation of innovative and creative communication and networking researchers.</p>	Sec 3	D6.1 identifies the KPI for this D&C activity. D6.2 and D6.3 will report on the progress made.

WP6 5G-ROUTES Deliverables

D6.1: Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v1.0

Initial report containing the dissemination and communication plans and activities implemented.

D6.2: Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v2.0

Interim report containing the dissemination and communication plans and activities implemented.

D6.3: Dissemination & Communication plans and activities final version

Final report containing the dissemination and communication plans and activities implemented.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The structure of the deliverable is as follows. First, in Section 3, we present the plan for the dissemination activities of the project. Then, Section 4 describes the planned communication activities. Section 5 provides details about the time plan of the dissemination and communication phases, Section 6 shows the specific dissemination and communication plan per partner, Section 8 lists the metrics of interest and the targets for these activities. Finally, Section 9 includes the conclusions and next actions for this task.

2.3 Linkage to Other Project Outputs

This section shows the interdependencies of this deliverable with other deliverables, see Table 2.

Table 2: Interdependencies between deliverables

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D6.4 Project Website and Social Media Presence [2]	Sections 3 (Project's Website) and section 4 (Project's Social Media Channels)	Sections 3 and 4 introduces the website of the project and the social media channels which are referenced in this deliverable (section 4.2 Communication Channels)
OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
No outputs utilised by other deliverables		

3 Dissemination Activities

This section outlines how the project will establish and organise the dissemination actions to promote the project and the adoption of its outcomes beyond its lifetime.

3.1 Target Audience and Objectives

The general objective of the joint 5G-ROUTES dissemination strategy is to disclose project results that can be used by specific target audiences to progress their own work, i.e. to build upon the knowledge generated by 5G-ROUTES, fertilising the advancement of technology, science, industry and policy. 5G-ROUTES has identified a number of target audiences (see Table 3). The specific joint dissemination activities will be tailored to the needs and profile of the target audience.

Table 3: Target audience groups for dissemination

Target audience	Description	Dissemination Objectives
Academia & RTOs	Institutions primarily for education and early research for expanding their academic skills	To consider the results in updated curricula, advanced courses and new R&I initiatives
Public R&I	Institutions with innovation-oriented R&D and technology transfer (e.g. EU Investment Bank, Start-Up Europe, EC Digital Innovation Hubs)	To adopt the results in technology transfer and new R&I initiatives with industry
Government	Governmental agencies and authorities mainly concerned with policy setting (e.g. road traffic, railway traffic, port traffic authorities)	To consider the results in policy and new regulatory developments for CAM
IT experts from SMEs	Developers of new applications creating strong links with academia, RTOs and leading industrial entities, creating a strong value chain	To adopt the results for developing new innovative CAM applications, and to create strong links with industry and academia
Public/Private associations	Initiatives that leverage public and private resources and funds for joint undertakings (e.g. 5G-PPP, EIT Digital, European Private Equity)	To consider the results in the planning of joint public and private undertakings
Vehicle OEMs	Integrate intelligence and 5G communication components in vehicles for enabling CAM services	To adopt project's results in vehicles and in the planning of new features
Industrial equipment vendors	Private companies that maintain R&I groups for new product and services, e.g. telecom vendors, tier-1/tier-2 suppliers, vertical stakeholders	To adopt the results in product and service roadmaps, plan new products, services and future R&I initiatives
Telecom infrastructure providers and MNOs	The potential offered by innovative CAM services enables telecom providers to expand their service offerings, thereby increasing market share and growth rate.	To enhance and upgrade their existing telecom and mobile infrastructure to enable the offering of CAM services with guaranteed SLAs.

3.2 Dissemination Channels

A major element for dissemination relates to the joint and coordinated participation in relevant activities of the 5G-PPP¹ and the 5G Infrastructure Association (5G-IA). 5G-ROUTES will contribute to the brochures and other material coordinated at 5G-PPP level, such as the “*European 5G Annual Journal*”², the 5G-PPP projects brochure³ and other material including videos⁴, as requested by the 5G-IA and/or the Full5G CSA of the 5G-PPP. Furthermore, 5G-ROUTES has identified channels for the dissemination of the project’s results to scientific, technology and industry communities and specific activities which will be tailored to the needs, clients and events that will be used. More specifically, the target audience and the dissemination channels will be actively monitored and selected to achieve the highest possible impact in geographic areas relative to the partners’ own planned activities. Table 4 provides an outline of the target audience and channels.

Table 4: Dissemination channels and activities

Target audience	Channels
Universities, RTOs, Industry through International conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IEEE GLOBECOM, IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021-2023, IEEE 5G Summit 2021-2023, ITS World Congress, Journal of Rail Transport Planning & Management, International Conference on Smart Transportation and Future Mobility, EUCAD 2021-2023, etc.
Universities, RTOs, Industry through scientific journals and magazines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), Elsevier Vehicular Communications, IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, Springer journals, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communication, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.
Universities, RTOs, Industry, Public authorities through Dedicated Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of a focused group workshop by ATOS and ILS by M27 to analyse the responses from questionnaires and surveys from the end-users of the CAM vertical sector providers (i.e. automotive, railways, transport & logistics, infotainment) so as to provide technical, business, security, privacy, policy and regulatory recommendations on the provision of cross-border CAM services. Organisation of two scientific workshops, open to academic and industrial communities, to present the intermediate and the final results, which will be co-located with important conferences. The 1st workshop will be organised by CERTH and VED by M25 (June 2022 at EuCNC/Global5G), and the 2nd by IQU and CTTC by M33 (Feb 2023 at MWC).
Universities, RTOs, Industry, Public/Private associations through the 5G-PPP and other 5G CAM initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution of project’s results to the 5G-PPP through its Work Groups, including participation to the dedicated monthly calls with other 5G-PPP projects to align the overall dissemination efforts. Interactions with worldwide fora and initiatives, e.g. 5G-AA, CAR2CAR Communication Consortium, ERTICO (where AIRBUS, VTT, VED and CERTH are active members), International Union of

¹ <https://5g-ppp.eu/>

² 2020 edition at <https://bscw.5g-ppp.eu/pub/bscw.cgi/d356008/Full%205G%20Annual%20Journal%202020.pdf>

³ Current edition available at <https://5g-ppp.eu/flayer-brochure/>

⁴ Project videos at <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-3-videos-now-available/>

	<p>Railways, EU Rail Infrastructure Managers, etc., for the effective dissemination of project results and cross-fertilisation of ideas and concepts.</p>
<p>Government, Industry, IT experts through Industrial Exhibitions, Business Conferences and Trade Fairs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile World Congress-MWC-(2021-2023): Present results and activities related to the project’s use-cases to generate an ecosystem for 5G CAM validation closely related to the MWC. Members of the consortium will participate in the annual MWC events (e.g. ADS, ATOS, CTTC, EEE, TTU, VTT) and present innovations inspired from 5G-ROUTES. • EUCNC, Global 5G events, Connected Automated Driving (2021-2023): Present demos of use cases and results. BRA will showcase project outcomes at IBC (Amsterdam) and NAB (Las Vegas) broadcasting trade fairs.
<p>Universities, RTOs through Academic dissemination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination to the academic community, of key results for use in teaching and training programs, for the preparation of educational material for technical schools and universities, detailed presentations and guidebooks for professionals. On-line project presentations on 5G-ROUTES scientific topics publicly available through the project’s website. Organisation of 3 tutorials under the framework of important IEEE conferences listed above and 2 PhD schools by CTTC to inspire M.Sc. and Ph.D. students to become the next generation of EU communication and networking researchers.

4 Communication Activities

4.1 Target Audience and Objectives

The following Table 5 provides an outline of the target audiences of the communication strategy and their interest in 5G-ROUTES.

Table 5: Target audience groups for communication

Target Group	Description	Interest in the project
A - Industry, SMEs and Entrepreneurs	Stakeholders from industry, network operators, SMEs and entrepreneurs, operating in the 5G CAM domain (e.g. EU MNOs, OTT providers, 5G AA, 5G ACIA, CAR2CAR, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilisation of project's results in operations and in their R&I activities for new service and product development. Amplify innovation in 5G CAM by blending 5G-ROUTES results with in-house artefacts
B - 5G PPP infrastructure Programme Stakeholders	Participants, project partners and relevant stakeholders active in the 5G PPP Work Groups, other 5G-PPP projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of common topics Synergies and collaborations for results promotion Enhancing innovation through results combination Co-organisation of events
C – Technology Clusters	European initiatives and clusters, research communities, associations, (e.g. ETNO, NetWorld2020, Digital Business Innovation, Digital Agenda, Innovation Union, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers...) Dissemination of project's results to their members Participation in project's events for knowledge exchange
D – Researchers and Academics	Researchers and academics working in universities, research centres, R&I departments of industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advancing research post-project Training personnel and students Porting results to real-life industry cases
E – Policy Makers	Policy-makers at any level (e.g. Council of Regions, EC Directorate for Communication, European Radio Spectrum Policy Group)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation of the project's techno-economic and regulatory aspects Definition of future research and innovation directions based on project's acquired knowledge
F – Standards bodies and fora	Standards bodies, industry fora, open-source organisations (e.g. 3GPP, ETSI, IETF, NGMN, IEEE, ITU-T, ISO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of roadmaps for standards development Input for standardisation activities
G – General Public	General public and anyone interested in the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the value of European research Stimulate innovation in unexpected groups of society

Based on the target audience groups identified above and their expected interest in the project, the objectives of the joint communication strategy and their relation to the target audience groups are identified in Table 6.

Table 6: Communication objectives

Objectives Description	Target groups						
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Provide a clear view of the project goals and its results, including the 5G-PPP perspective	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Create an active community of interested stakeholders and potential users and collect knowledge and requirements considered by the project's activities	●	●	●	●	●	●	
Prepare the ground for the exploitation of project's results towards the industry	●	●				●	
Create awareness of the project among the full range of stakeholders impacted by the results	●	●	●	●		●	
Establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge and innovation transfer		●	●	●	●	●	
Support the dissemination and exploitation of results (including the 5G PPP programme results) by formulating adapted key messages, and prepare adapted communication material	●		●	●		●	
Recognition of the results (including the 5G-PPP programme results) among the research communities, standardisation bodies, potential users, policy-maker institutions.		●	●	●	●	●	

4.2 Communication Channels

The 5G-ROUTES communication strategy combines a mix of traditional and disruptive communication channels:

- Online presence:** A project website was created in M01 and **maintained by EBOS** serving to: i) promote the project's public image and serve as a main online access point for the different target groups; ii) serve as an information source, highlighting project objectives, activities, outcomes and relevant updates; iii) serve as a repository of information. Since the website will be publicly accessible, it will be used as an online repository for public deliverables and publications, that will be free to download: <https://www.5g-routes.eu/dissemination-communication/public-deliverables/>. In addition, the website will also feature a restricted area, only accessible to project partners, the EC project scientific officer and the project review panel team: this restricted area contains documents and confidential information related to the project's internal activities and reporting. The initial page of the website is depicted Figure 1. A detailed description and analysis of the project's website is described in D6.4, "Project website and social media presence" which was submitted in M1 of the Project.

Figure 1: 5G-ROUTES website

- **Press and TV/Radio Interviews:** 5G-ROUTES will publish at least 5 press releases (1-2 per year) in order to show major achievements and the potential of 5G as a future-proof technology for CAM services. The consortium will attempt to reach the general audience via TV/radio interviews. **LMT will be responsible for this activity.**
- **Brochures/flyers:** 5G-ROUTES will prepare 3 technical brochures providing information about the technical and scientific achievements and 3 non-technical brochures-factsheets describing the potential project applications and services in a more accessible manner. The brochures will be also distributed to local universities, schools, city councils, recreational areas, etc. **CTTC will lead this activity.**
- **Social media:** 5G-ROUTES will use several online social media sites, such as Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, as a two-way access between the project partners and the technical and public audience. The consortium will regularly publish announcements and initiate discussions from month M06. The content will be updated on a regular basis and the obtained feedback will help to influence the project's directions. **IQU will coordinate this activity.** Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows the YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn social media channels of 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 2: 5G-ROUTES YouTube Channel

Figure 3: 5G-ROUTES Twitter

5G-ROUTES Project
Research

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About us

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, it will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland. This will help to boost confidence and accelerate the deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services throughout Europe.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951867.

Website	https://www.5g-routes.eu/
Industries	Research
Company size	51-200 employees
Headquarters	Brussels
Type	Partnership
Founded	2020

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Figure 4: 5G-ROUTES LinkedIn profile

- **Video clips:** 2 video clips will be produced, which will cover the 5G-ROUTES general ideas, demonstrations and presentations and talks that will also include non-technical information about the project, targeting non-expert public. The videos will be available at the project's website during the entire project's lifetime, while a dedicated link will be used in order to request feedback from the audience. **This activity will be coordinated by CTTC.**
- **Newsletters:** These will be distributed to different mailing lists, to foster inter-communication with other relevant research actions, projects and technical communities. The newsletters, available at the project's website, will provide information regarding the project activities, achievements and results, targeting cross-fertilisation. The first issue will be released at M06 and new issues every 6 months. **CTTC will coordinate this activity.**
- **Public engagement:** 5G-ROUTES consortium members will follow a set of strategies to interact with the general public (e.g. non-scientists, secondary schools, etc.) and inform them about the effect of the 5G-ROUTES results in their everyday life and to create awareness on the differences about facts regarding the societal benefits of the 5G CAM technologies. This set of activities include the use of social media, online

video-clips, public talks at schools and university open days, participation at events organised by the local authorities, etc.

Table 7 shows the list of responsible partners for each one of the communication channels.

Table 7: Responsible partners

Communication activity	Responsible partner
Website	EBOS
Press releases	LMT
Brochures/flyers	CTTC
Social media	IQU
Video clips	CTTC
Newsletters	CTTC

5G-ROUTES press releases should be revised and approved by LMT before publication. LMT will ensure that the press release is not biased and does not contain confidential information.

5 Dissemination and Communication Phases

Dissemination and communication activities will be carried out in four phases following experience acquired in related projects, other works, regulations and best practices learned in the past. Each of these phases have their own objectives and target audience groups and will perform the activities using the best-suited channels. These D&C phases will be discussed and aligned with other projects of the 5G-PPP programme in order to achieve an optimum mix of dissemination and communication for 5G-ROUTES and the 5G-PPP programme at large. Table 8 presents the four 5G-ROUTES dissemination phases in detail.

Table 8: 5G-ROUTES Dissemination and Communication (D&C)

Type of information	Target audience	Channels	Goals
D&C Phase 1 (Create awareness) M1-M12 Objective: To create awareness about the project's objectives and expected results for as many 5G Stakeholders as possible, leveraging the awareness that has already been created around the 5G-PPP programme.			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of 5G-ROUTES • Objectives and expected results of 5G-ROUTES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry, technological, research and academia • Potential end-users • International Stakeholders identified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences, workshops • Brochures, roll-ups, posters • Website • Social media channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General visibility • Attract potential customers, investors and collaborators
D&C Phase 2 (Accelerate potential impact) M13-M26 Objective: To kick-start and boost the potential impact of the project through the elaboration of the use cases, leveraging the achieved awareness of D&C Phase 1 to reach out to target stakeholder groups.			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presenting elaborated use cases of 5G-ROUTES • Demonstration of usage and results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential end-users • Specific technological, research and academic communities • 5G vendors and application developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences, workshops • Publications in journals • Special sessions in major congresses/exhibitions • Website • Social media channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposing synergies with other 5G-PPP projects • Providing visibility • Informing EC authorities • Attracting potential collaborators
D&C Phase 3 (Results) M27-M33 Objective: To leverage general awareness, to emphasise the use of the 5G-ROUTES offerings and results, and to attract users and customers of the project's partners, thus increasing the impact through external collaboration.			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presenting elaborated use cases of 5G-ROUTES • Demonstration of usage and results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential end-users • Potential developers in ICT companies • Specific technological, research and academic communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences, workshops • Publications in journals • Special sessions in major congresses/exhibitions • Website • Social media channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attracting potential investors • Attracting potential customers
D&C Phase 4 (Valorisation) M34-M36 and >M36 Objective: To demonstrate the usefulness of the results to internal and external users and customers and to attract investors. To consolidate and publish the final scientific and business findings of the project in national/international journals and online media.			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final results of 5G-ROUTES • User oriented demonstration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential end-users • Potential developers in ICT companies • Specific technological, research and academic communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Publications in journals • Industry focused events • Client demonstrations and demos in major 5G events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attracting potential customers • Attracting investors • Informing the EC Authorities • Demonstrating results to existing customers

6 Dissemination and Communication Plan

Table 9 specifies the dissemination and communication plans for each partner during the 3 years of the project.

Table 9: 5G-ROUTES Dissemination and Communication Plan

Partner	Year	Planned Dissemination and Communication Activities
EEE	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to joint IEEE publications Contribute to joint publication of conference papers Participate in International conferences. Participate in local 5G and mobility events. Contribute to Social media accounts Prepare International press releases Prepare Local press releases
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to joint IEEE publications Contribute to joint publication of conference papers Participate in International conferences. Participate in local 5G and mobility events. Contribute to Social media accounts Prepare International press releases Prepare Local press releases Contribute to joint press releases with partners about UC trials Contribute to organizing PhD school 1
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to joint IEEE publications Contribute to joint publication of conference papers Participate in International conferences. Participate in local 5G and mobility events. Contribute to Social media accounts Prepare International press releases Prepare Local press releases Contribute to joint press releases with partners about UC trials Contribute to organizing PhD school 2 Contribute with partners in making a video about the project Contribute in publishing guidelines to universities how to integrate the knowledge to courses
ADS	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are no specific plans for this partner. This partner will contribute to general dissemination and communication activities that will be reported accordingly.
	Y2	
	Y3	
ADSF	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are no specific plans for this partner. This partner will contribute to general dissemination and communication activities that will be reported accordingly.
	Y2	
	Y3	
PV	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are no specific plans for this partner. This partner will contribute to general dissemination and communication activities that will be reported accordingly.
	Y2	
	Y3	
ATOS	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication action about 5G-ROUTES within Atos business units Include 5G-ROUTES information within Atos Research web booklet Post news in social media, e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter. Participate in EuCNC 2021 Contribute to the 5GPPP activities, e.g., Automotive Working Group, and Business Validation WG on behalf of 5G-ROUTES.
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to 2 technical papers. Participate in EuCNC 2022 and MWC 2022 Post news in social media, e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter. Contribute to newsletters Reporte WP2 5G-ROUTES results to OSM community – potential contribution regarding CAM repository.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to the 5GPPP activities, e.g., Automotive Working Group, and Business Validation WG on behalf of 5G-ROUTES
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to 1 paper. Communicate action about 5G-ROUTES results to Atos business units Post news in social media, e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter. Participate in EuCNC 2023 and MWC 2023 Contribute to the 5GPPP activities, e.g., Automotive Working Group, and Business Validation WG on behalf of 5G-ROUTES
BRA	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feed and share the social media channels of 5G ROUTES account. Link to project website from corporate website. Participate in the development of promotional material. Participate to conferences, broadcast fairs, workshops and events for presenting the project objectives and outcomes. Participate in activities organized jointly with other EU funded project(s) for exchanging knowledge and ideas.
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feed and share the social media channels of 5G ROUTES account. Link to project website from corporate website. Participate in the development of promotional material. Participate to conferences, broadcast fairs, workshops and events for presenting the project objectives and outcomes. Participate to NAB, the National Association of Broadcasters Show, and IBC event. Participate in activities organized jointly with other EU funded project(s) for exchanging knowledge and ideas.
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feed and share the social media channels of 5G ROUTES account. Link to project website from corporate website. Participate in the development of promotional material. Participate to conferences, broadcast fairs, workshops and events for presenting the project objectives and outcomes. Participate to NAB, the National Association of Broadcasters Show, and IBC event. Participate in activities organized jointly with other EU funded project(s) for exchanging knowledge and ideas.
CTC	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish a paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) Submit a paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) Publish a conference paper (e.g., IEEE MeditCom, IEEE Globecom, etc.) Organize a workshop or special session (IEEE MeditCom) Post news in social media Prepare 2 newsletters Contribute to the 5GPPP activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish a paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) Submit a paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) Publish a conference paper Organize a workshop or special session Post news in social media Prepare 2 newsletters Contribute to the 5GPPP activities Organize a PhD School Participation in international fairs (e.g., Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.) Demonstrations in exhibitions (e.g., IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSWC], Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.)

	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) • Submit a paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) • Publish a conference paper • Organize a workshop or special session • Post news in social media • Prepare 2 newsletters • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Organize a PhD School • Participation in international fairs (e.g., IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSWC], Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.) • Demonstrations in exhibitions (e.g., IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSWC], Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.)
EBOS	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and implement project’s website • Create project’s knowledge base • Post news in social media • Design factsheets, brochures, flyers • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update project’s website • Update project’s knowledge base • Post news in social media • Design additional dissemination material i.e., new brochures and flyers • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Publish a first paper presenting the Composite KPIs methodology used to assess the capability of 5G networks to support CAM applications in a scientific magazine (IEEE, EU Joint Research Center (JRC))
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update project’s website • Update project’s knowledge base • Post news in social media • Design additional dissemination material i.e. new brochures and flyers • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Publish a second paper presenting the assessment of the capability of 5G networks to support CAM applications done in 5G-ROUTES in a scientific magazine (IEEE, EU Joint Research Center (JRC))
EVR	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no specific plans for this partner. This partner will contribute to general dissemination and communication activities that will be reported accordingly.
	Y2	
	Y3	
ENIDE	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retweet 5G-ROUTES posts on Twitter • Share 5G-ROUTES posts on LinkedIn • Distribute flyers, factsheets, and brochures when possible
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retweet 5G-ROUTES posts on Twitter • Share 5G-ROUTES posts on LinkedIn • Distribute flyers, factsheets, and brochures when possible
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retweet 5G-ROUTES posts on Twitter • Share 5G-ROUTES posts on LinkedIn • Distribute flyers, factsheets, and brochures when possible
CERTH	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submit a conference paper (IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference)
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submit a paper to an IEEE Journal (IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, etc.) • Publish two conference papers (EuCNC, IEEE Globecom, TRA, ITS Congress, etc.) • Organise two Use Case workshops/ demo events focusing on business impact with external stakeholders

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post news in social media
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submit a paper to an IEEE Journal (IEEE Communications Magazine, Elsevier Future Generation Computer Systems, etc.) • Submit a paper to Advanced Microsystems for Automotive Applications (AMAA, Elsevier) • Organise two Use Case workshops/ demo events focusing on business impact with external stakeholders • Publish three conference papers and organise/ co-organise a special session in a key congress (EuCNC, IEEE Globecom, ITS Congress, etc.) • Demonstration of UC3.3 in one selected event/Exhibition • Post news in social media
ILS	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no specific plans for this partner. This partner will contribute to general dissemination and communication activities that will be reported accordingly.
	Y2	
	Y3	
VED	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no specific plans for this partner. This partner will contribute to general dissemination and communication activities that will be reported accordingly.
	Y2	
	Y3	
IQU	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a paper in an IEEE Journal (IEEE Communications Magazine) • Publish a conference paper (IEEE MeditCom) • Organise a special session (IEEE MeditCom) • Post news in social media
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a conference paper • Post news in social media • Demonstration in one exhibition (e.g., IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSmart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.)
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) • Publish two conference papers • Post news in social media • Demonstration in one exhibition (e.g., IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSWC], Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.)
LMT	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in International conferences: 5G-TECHRITORY Forum • Participate in local 5G and mobility events: Urban Mobility Hackathon, Discussion festival LAMPA 2021, TechChill 2021 • Publish info about the project on the LMT Innovations website • Contribute to LMT Social media accounts • Prepare International press releases • Prepare Local press releases
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participance in GITEX Technology week • Participate in 5GAA events (5G Techritory discussion) • Participate in Discussion forum LAMPA 2022, 5G-TECHRITORY 2021, Tech Chill 2022 • Participate in Vefresh events and hackathons • Teleoperated self-driving Demo follow up • Story line in TV3 “Technologies without instructions” • Prepare Local Press releases - at least 5 • Prepare International Press releases • Post in LMT Innovation social media accounts
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in 5GAA events • Participate in Discussion forum LAMPA 2023, 5G-TECHRITORY 2022, Tech Chill 2023 • Participate in Vefresh events and hackathons • Teleoperated self-driving Demo follow up • Prepare Local Press releases - at least 5 • Prepare International Press releases • Post in LMT Innovation social media accounts

SWM	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post news in social media • Prepare a newsletter • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities (i.e., 5G CAM WG, Vision and Societal Challenges WG)
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post news in social media • Prepare a newsletter (e.g., TTS Italia) • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities (i.e., 5G CAM WG, Vision and Societal Challenges WG) • Submit a paper to a conference (e.g., ITS world congress, ITS European congress, etc.)
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post news in social media • Prepare a newsletter (e.g., TTS Italia) • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities (i.e., 5G CAM WG, Vision and Societal Challenges WG) • Submit a paper to a conference (e.g., ITS world congress, ITS European congress, etc.)
TTU	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) • Submit 1 paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) • Publish 1-3 conference papers (e.g., IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc.) • Contribute to organizing a workshop or special session (IEEE MeditCom) • Post news in social media/University Website/Research information portal • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE ACCESS, etc.) • Submit 1 paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Systems Journal, etc.) • Publish 1-3 conference papers (e.g., IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc.) • Publish 1 paper in a journal special issue, and/or organize 1 journal special issue • Organize 1 (online) tutorial in framework of important IEEE conference (e.g. IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc.) • Post news in social media/University Website/Research information portal • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Contribute to organization of the first PhD School (lead by CTTC) • Participate in international fairs (e.g., Mobile World Congress [MWC], IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSWC], Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.) • Use key results in teaching material, e.g., MSc course “System Aspects of Communication” at Tallinn University of Technology
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 paper in an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.) • Submit 1 paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE ACCESS, IEEE Journal, Internet of Things Journal, etc.) • Publish 1-3 conference papers (e.g., IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc.) • Organize 2 (online) tutorials in framework of important IEEE conference (e.g., IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc.) • Post news in social media/University Website/Research information portal • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Contribute to organization of the second PhD School (lead by CTTC) • Participation in international fairs (e.g., Mobile World Congress [MWC], IoT Solutions World Congress [IoTSWC], Smart City Expo World Congress [SCEWC], European Conference on Networks and Communications [EUCNC], etc.) • Use key results in teaching material, e.g., MSc course “System Aspects in Communications” at Tallinn University of Technology
VTT	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a conference paper (e.g., IEEE MeditCom.) • Post news in social media • Contribute to newsletters • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post news in social media • Attend national events (5GTN or 5G MOMENTUM)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a paper on an IEEE conference (IEEE 5G Intelligent Vehicles, IEEE 5G World Forum) or EUCNC 2022 • Contribute to newsletters
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a paper on the ITS World or ITS Europe conference • Submit a paper to an IEEE Journal (e.g., IEEE ITS, etc.) • Submit a scientific paper to EUCNC 2023 • Post news in social media • Contribute to 2 newsletters • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities
TELIA	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare and post 2 national level bulletins about the project • Talk about the project in public radio (2 instances) • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare and post 2 national level bulletins about the project • Talk about the project in public radio (2 instances) • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Contribute to joint PR activities with TalTech, Ericsson and LMT
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare and post 2 national level bulletins about the project • Prepare and disseminate a video about the project • Contribute to the 5GPPP activities • Contribute to joint PR activities with TalTech, Ericsson and LMT
VEDIA	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate on national workshops, webinars and seminars • Post news in social media • Prepare 1 blogpost • Contribute to the project deliverables and other dissemination activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate on national/international workshops, webinars and seminars • Post news in social media • Prepare 2 blogpost • Contribute to the project deliverables and other dissemination activities • Contribute to the joint papers
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate on national/international workshops, webinars and seminars • Post news in social media • Prepare 2 blogpost • Contribute to the project deliverables and other dissemination activities • Contribute to the joint papers
WINGS	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare a presentation for the IEEE Meditcom workshop. • Prepare a presentation at the InfoCom World 2020 in Greece • Prepare a presentation at the FITCE Congress 2021 in Vienna
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present a talk in IEEE Meditcom workshop • Present 5G-ROUTES results in Infocom annual event in Greece • Present 5G-ROUTES enablers in FITCE
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present 5G-ROUTES results to Infocom in Greece • Present 5G-ROUTES results to FITCE

To collect the communication and dissemination activities from each partner, an Excel file has been made available to the consortium. The file should be filled in by all the partners regularly. The content of the file will be useful to generate the Newsletters of the project and the upcoming D6.2 and D6.3 (interim and final report, respectively) deliverables.

7 Dissemination and Communication Guidelines

The following section defines the Dissemination and Communication guidelines. It is very important that all 5G-ROUTES partners follow these dissemination guidelines to achieve a consistent representation to the outside and fulfil all goals stated in the Grant Agreement.

7.1 Email Address for Dissemination and Communication Activities

The email distribution list created to connect the partners of WP6 and administrated by CTTC is the following: 5groutes-wp6@l listes.cttc.es. This mailing list is regularly used, e.g., for announcing the WP6 calls and communicating any important activity to the WP partners.

In case one of the consortium partners has individual questions not covered by one of the following chapters, it is possible to use the mailing list above to contact the WP6 leader and simultaneously inform all persons that are responsible for the 5G-ROUTES dissemination of each partner.

Apart from the above mailing list, others have been created to help organization and communication between partners:

- General mailing list of the project: 5groutes-allpartners@l listes.cttc.es
- WP leaders mailing list: 5groutes-wpleaders@l listes.cttc.es
- Task leaders mailing list: 5groutes-taskleaders@l listes.cttc.es
- WP1 mailing list: 5groutes-wp1@l listes.cttc.es
- WP2 mailing list: 5groutes-wp2@l listes.cttc.es
- WP3 mailing list: 5groutes-wp3@l listes.cttc.es
- WP4 mailing list: 5groutes-wp4@l listes.cttc.es
- WP5 mailing list: 5groutes-wp5@l listes.cttc.es

All the mailing lists of the 5G-ROUTES project are administrated by CTTC.

7.2 Announcing upcoming publications

The 5G-ROUTES project depends on the scientific dissemination of project results by consortium partners. For this purpose, this guideline contains all necessary steps in a systematic manner.

All actions described in this chapter should be announced at least 45 days prior to the planned publication submission date.

1. Prepare the abstract/paper/poster according to scientific discipline.
 - a. If the content of the publication consists of parts from other consortium members, ask for clearance for publication from all involved parties.
 - b. Send the publication (short abstract in case of a scientific publication) at 5groutes-wp6@l listes.cttc.es including the following information:
 - i. venue,
 - ii. date of event,
 - iii. link of event,
 - iv. attending auditorium,
 - v. prepared document for planned publication.
(at least 45 days prior to the submission date)
2. After the notification of the planned publication, consortium members can make written objections within 30 days as response to the notification at 5groutes-wp6@l listes.cttc.es, or directly to the publishing partner. If there are no objectives within 30 days after the notification the publication can be published. Silence constitutes agreement.
 - a. Objections shall include, to the extent possible, a precise request for necessary modifications.

- b. Publishing party and objecting party shall discuss how to overcome the justified ground.
 - c. Objections include results, background and/or confidential information from the objecting party.
 - d. Publications may not be delayed more than 4 months, when objections have been removed.
3. If objections are raised, the publication must be revised accordingly.
 - a. A new notification to the consortium must be decided case by case as part of the necessary revisions.
4. Prepare the document for publication. All publications must include the funding acknowledgement for the 5G-ROUTES project:
“5G-ROUTES project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951867”
5. When the publication has been presented/published add the details required to the Dissemination and Communication Excel file. The project website will be updated regularly with this information.

In case of events attendance, where the 5G-ROUTES project is represented, it is important to inform the consortium (sending an email at 5groutes-wp6@LLISTES.CTTC.ES). This would help to know if someone from the consortium will attend the specific event to connect and collaborate.

8 Metrics and Targets

Table 10 lists the dissemination and communication metrics and their corresponding target values. The last column shows the metrics at month M14 (October 2021). Dissemination and communication activities will be reported in detail in the next deliverables D6.2 and D6.3. The website of the project has been updated with the most relevant dissemination and communication activities (<https://www.5g-routes.eu/dissemination-communication/>).

Table 10: Dissemination and communication outcome, metrics and targets

Dissemination Activities			
Activity/Metrics	Description	Target value	Current value (M14)
Industrial exhibitions	Participation in exhibitions	>9	1
	Exhibition booths	>3	1
Scientific publications	Journals/magazines	>9	2
	Conferences	>20	4
	Conference demonstrations	>6	0
Workshops/surveys	Technical workshops	2	1
	Participants per technical workshop	>70	15
	Focused group workshop surveys	1	0
	Participants per focused group	>100	0
5G-PPP Programme	Number of WGs to contribute	7	7
	Interactions with fora/initiatives	>4	NA
Training	Online tutorials	3	0
	Number of PhD schools	2	0
Online repository	Number of publicly available deliverables	>20	7
Communication Activities			
Activity/Metrics	Description	Target value	Current value (M14)
Project website	Online by	M1	Yes
	Unique visitors from M12	1000	>1000
	Unique visitors from M36	2000	NA
Social media	LinkedIn group followers	>200	138
	Twitter followers	>200	116
	Re-Tweets	>200	16
	Facebook followers	>200	Not created
	Facebook likes	>1000	Not created
	Banners	>30	0
	Press releases / Newsletters	Press releases	>5
Newsletters		>6	1
Factsheets / Brochures	Technical factsheets	3	0
	Non-technical factsheets	3	1
	Hardcopies	>1000	250
Video clips	Number of online video clips	2	0
	Number of video views	>1000	NA
Flyers / posters & roll-ups	Project flyers	>3	1
	Posters & roll-up banners	>3	1

So far, the Facebook social media channel has not been created since we consider that today LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube social media channels are more professional than a Facebook profile. However, it will be created later if the consortium considers it necessary.

9 Conclusions and Next Actions

This deliverable (D6.1) has provided the initial dissemination and communication plan of the 5G-ROUTES project. Regarding the dissemination activities, we have identified the target audience and the main dissemination channels that will be exploited during the project for the dissemination of the technical outcome and results. In particular, it is expected that the most important project developments will be disseminated through:

- i) Publications in scientific journals and prestigious conferences;
- ii) Demonstrations in fairs, exhibitions and EU-related events;
- iii) Online media, such as inputs to technical websites, webinars, etc.

Regarding the communication activities, the target audience and stakeholders have been also identified, while the qualitative communication objectives have been defined. In the same context, the most important communication channels (e.g., project's website, newsletters, event organization, etc.) have been also listed.

Besides the target audience and the channels for the dissemination activities, we have also provided a time plan for these activities, which includes 4 phases. The goal of the 1st phase (M1-M12) is to create awareness about 5G-ROUTES, while the 2nd phase (M13-M26) is expected to accelerate the potential impact of the project. The core results will be disseminated and communicated during the 3rd phase of the project (M27-M33), while the 4th phase (M34-M36 and beyond) will guarantee the valorisation of the project's outcome. Being in the 1st phase of dissemination and communication, our main goal is to create awareness about the project's objectives and expected results for as many 5G stakeholders as possible, leveraging the awareness that has already been created around the 5G-PPP programme.

Finally, D6.1 has also provided the quantified targets for the dissemination and communication activities in a 3-year horizon. The following deliverable D6.2 will include an interim report on dissemination and communication activities during the first half of 5G-ROUTES. At the end of the project, D6.3 will provide the final report on dissemination and communications activities carried out throughout the project.

10 References

[1] 5G-ROUTES Grant Agreement (number 951867)

[2] D6.4 Project Website and Social [Media](https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Attachment_6.4.pdf)

Presence: [https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-](https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Attachment_6.4.pdf)